

ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCES ON THE FORMATION OF ECO-LITERACY IN STUDENTS

Maksudova Gulnara Muhammadjonovna

Researcher of Fergana State University

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the formation of eco-literacy in students in the process of modernization of environmental education, pedagogical-psychological features of modernization of environmental education, the corrective effect of eco-creativity, eco-responsibility, eco-literacy competencies in students between nature and human relations studied. Modern pedagogical approaches to the modernization of environmental education are also analyzed.

Key words: ecology, biosphere, formation of eco-literacy, environment, national values, healthy lifestyle, ecological dialogue, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, value, value approach, national, historical, technological.

INTRODUCTION. Today, issues of environmental education are being considered with great attention on a global scale. Because the growing global ecological crisis, environmental pollution and other problems require the eco-movement to become an active force. In this regard, as the head of state noted: "The most important issue is that we must seriously focus on increasing the ecological culture of the population. Of course, such problems cannot be solved only by administrative means, it can be achieved by instilling in the hearts of the young generation love for mother nature and a sense of belonging to it. That is why ecological education and upbringing issues are being reformed at all levels of education, from pre-school educational institutions to higher education institutions. Therefore, one of the urgent tasks is to develop a general outlook of society and to form a rational attitude to nature through the development of continuous education.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Pedagogical foundations of ecological education are expressed in the research works of Academician I.D. Zverev, A.N. Zakhlebniy, the content, methodology, form, and tools of ecological education in teaching natural sciences by E.O. Turdigulov. The biological direction of ecological education was studied by I. T. Suravegina, as well as socio-philosophical aspects by Y. Shodimetov, B. Ziyomukhamedov. In the researches of L.T.Shonosirova, G.O.Komilova, environmental education of preschool children, and in the researches of M.A.Yuldashev, M.M.Abdullayeva, M.B.Rahimkulova, G.Sultonova, N.Ashurova, issues of environmental knowledge in primary education were studied.

Abroad, scientists R.G. Barker, W.R. Catton, D.D. Chiras, R.E. Dunlap, the content and essence, structure of environmental education; the issues of creating eco-literacy in students were mentioned in the scientific research of D.H. Meadows, D. L. Meadows, J. Randers, A. W. Wiecker, Ch. M. Geesteranus, J. C. Smith, L. F. Schmore, A. J. Suvan, O. D. Duncan, S. Foresman, and U. Halbach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. According to international standards, environmental education includes education about the environment, with the help of the environment, and for the environment. These three components provide a holistic solution to the fragmented issues of environmental education and upbringing. For example, in Western Europe, environmental education and upbringing begins at the age of three, through children interacting with wild and domestic animals in special farms, and even taking care of them.

Educational work in the regions and countries that are among the top 20 "ecologically clean" countries, the formation of the potential of "Ecologically cultured person" starts from the pre-school educational institution. The main goal of this is to create the first elements of ecological culture in MTT students through environmental education and training. In general, in Western Europe, they try to create all the conditions for children to communicate with wild and domestic animals in special farms and to start environmental education and upbringing from the age of three by taking care of them.

In order to use the world's experience and eliminate such non-ecological education, in the above-mentioned joint decision adopted by the Ministry of Ecology and Environmental Protection and Preschool Education, measures are implemented to establish environmental science in MTT. the issue is raised. This also shows the need to form an ecological culture and a worldview of environmental protection for the students.

Also, this paragraph analyzes the effectiveness of studying, researching and introducing the experience of foreign countries and the practice of developed countries in the field of environmental education in the education system. Therefore, we considered it appropriate to bring the experience of developed countries.

In Austria, preparation for professional environmental education and upbringing is included in school programs. For example:

- organization of special school projects;
- ("School garden", "Environmental history", "Ecology at school", "Ecological workshop", "Creativity for nature");
- carrying out nature protection actions ("Ozone", "Alpine activities");
- preparation of various didactic materials and special training manuals related to ecology;
- organization of seminars for pedagogues-ecologists and retraining courses of all specialists involved in environmental education of students;
- publication of magazines and newspapers on environmental education issues;
- "Environment, school and community" preparation of special environmental education programs in this direction;
- creation of a national data bank on environmental education issues; implementation of coordination functions;
- the teachers and other specialists give consultations to children who express their desire to participate in environmental education, school and extracurricular environmental education, various projects related to environmental education.

At the stage of higher professional education in Austria, environmental education begins directly with the teaching of special and professional subjects on the basis of a choice. General environmental education and training is included in the general education system.

In Denmark, the problems of environmental education and upbringing are included in all pedagogical professional education systems. Compulsory environmental education,

interdisciplinary independent education, and the popularity of relevant educational materials in the training of pedagogues. Denmark to hold Nordic Symposium with Scandinavian countries and international "Environmental Education in Scandinavia", "Baltic Sea", "North Sea" and "Clean Rivers", "Acid Rain", "Green Flag" is a permanent participant of long-term cooperation projects through the implementation of national educational projects, mapping and studying the ecological condition of sea coasts.

German environmental education is aimed at changing young people's perception of the environment and developing their knowledge, increasing their readiness to protect nature, and forming environmentally responsible behavior in the growing generation. The main emphasis is on revealing the relationship between man, society and the natural environment. There are opinions that the human factor is the main factor in ecological education and upbringing, which leads to the destructive pollution of ecosystems.

In Ireland, environmental education and training is aimed at solving the following issues: helping to explain the complexity of the relationship between man and the natural environment; stimulate interest in economic, social, political and ecological relations in cities and villages; to provide each student with the knowledge, attitudes, values and skills to make responsible environmental decisions and the practical knowledge and skills necessary to protect and improve the natural environment; to create and implement new ecological models of behavior and activity in the environment in individual, group and collective consciousness, to help form a new attitude to nature in individual citizens, different social groups and communities; to help the population to acquire broad practical environmental skills; identification and classification of environmental problems, solving problematic issues and situations, participating in the process of accepting solutions to environmental problems.

In Sweden, environmental education and training was created in 1970 in preparation for the "European Year of the Environment" and on the eve of its implementation, and the topic of environmental protection was included in the new nine-year compulsory education. At the same time, the National Program on environmental issues was prepared and adopted. According to his requirements, new educational manuals and guidelines for teachers and students were published in Sweden. Environmental education and training has become a primary issue in the cooperation of the European countries located on the Scandinavian Peninsula. A nationwide information system on environmental education issues has been created in cooperation with the Swedish Environmental Protection Society and the National Agency for Education.

In Japan, the preparation of a person with a high ecological spirituality was achieved through environmental education programs, which included all stages of national professional training. The Japanese are not very religious, so instead of icons, they have a vase of flowers as an altar of beauty. Ikebana is known to all people on planet Earth. The Japanese attitude to nature is a special national psychology based on collective consciousness. That is why environmental education has an ancient history and has developed by ensuring the harmony of corporate-pedagogical, motivational, environment-friendly, reflexive, pedagogical-psychological forces with rationality.

In the United States of America, environmental education and upbringing have different forms, directions and methodological approaches. Deep penetration of environmental ethics into all educational and training content, formation of a careful and responsible attitude of the

population to the environment is carried out with the involvement of the general public, especially non-governmental public organizations.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, foreign experience shows that environmental education is not only directed towards specialization, but also aimed at the education of a person with high ecological spirituality. In foreign countries, environmental education and training is carried out in a way that originates from national mentality and regional characteristics. All directions and specializations of professional education are ecologized and systematized. That is why environmental education and training is studied based on the conditions of each state and locality, and its normative foundations are created.

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